

Education and Engagement in the Era of Social Distancing

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The birth of NOIRLab and the uniting of diverse programs and activities from sites in Tucson, Chile, and Hawai'i offer exciting challenges with myriad opportunities. Specifically, the transition of the Communications, Education and Engagement (CEE) group is now well underway—resulting in dozens of press and image releases over the past year, multiple internal and external publications (including this newsletter), professional conference coordination (e.g., AAS), and many more activities too numerous to list.

Among these successes are many challenges. Arguably, one of the greatest challenges has been to unite all of NOIRLab's Education and Engagement (E&E) programming in the era of COVID-19 social distancing. Just a year ago, visiting local classrooms and interacting directly with students was trivial—now it's impossible. Where once accommodating visitors at our telescopes was routine, we now focus on virtual experiences to share our facilities. Programs like Globe at Night, Journey Through the Universe, Viaje al Universo, Colors of Nature, Teen Astronomy Café, and AstroDay all rely on high levels of direct, in-person interaction, but with social distancing the current norm, new models utilizing virtual programming are necessary.

Figure 1. Alexis-Ann Acohido explores Gemini North with interactive iPad version of the Gemini Virtual Tour. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

In addition to adapting previously “in-person” programming to virtual delivery, the expansion and adaptation of virtual experiences, like the long-running Live from Gemini program, and virtual tours, have found new relevance in core NOIRLab E&E programming.

It is reasonable to expect that the development of new and expanded virtual programming will extend well into the post-COVID-19 era. Meanwhile, virtual programming expands participation globally and far beyond the local host community audiences traditionally targeted by many of our educational programs.

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The Teen Astronomy Café program, a long-running staple of local outreach in Tucson, is an example of an effective adaptation of previously in-person programming. “When

social distancing became commonplace, we wondered how we could still do Teen Astronomy Café,” said Connie Walker, who has led the program since 2017. “*Then we started looking at the tools available and prototyped a virtual version of the program,”* Walker adds. “*In the end it worked amazingly well and we continue to move the program forward and experiment with new ways to engage students.*” Expanding the program to all NOIRLab sites and beyond is also on the horizon.

This program was adapted as an early virtual program and continues to be offered with pandemic protocols. It is expected that a virtual version of this program will continue beyond COVID-19 and attract new audiences across the NOIRLab sites.

Another example, one that required less adaptation, is the expansion of the Live from Gemini program. For over a decade, this virtual (hosted) program provided classrooms and public audiences an opportunity to visit the Gemini control rooms, meet staff, and participate in a behind-the-scenes exploration of observatory operations and recent science highlights.

Expansion of this program in the COVID-19 era has resulted in a new name, Live from NOIRLab. Each site (Hawai'i, Tucson, and Chile) presents the program every third week (with the Chile version in Spanish), and features a staff or guest astronomer to share NOIRLab-relevant technology, science, and operations. A YouTube archive of these programs is available at [NOIRLabAstro](https://www.youtube.com/NOIRLabAstro) on YouTube.

Figure 2. Banner from a recent Live from NOIRLab event. These banners are used to promote the weekly programs on social media and on the events webpage. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

Figure 3: The Viaje al Universo program went virtual in October 2020 with virtual events, including this virtual star party led by CEE staff person Juan Seguel. During these star parties NOIRLab staff share objects currently visible in the night sky in the context of research at our facilities. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

The annual Viaje al Universo program in Chile was adapted to virtual delivery in October of 2020. The program, based on the Journey Through the Universe program in Hawai‘i, is based on in-person events in local classrooms and public talks and skygazing.

Adapting this program to virtual delivery presented many challenges. “At first we thought the program wasn’t adaptable to virtual delivery,” said program manager Manuel Paredes. “However, as we started looking at the situation we found ways to adapt the program, such as hosting virtual talks, workshops, and a star party, that will become regular elements in upcoming years even after social distancing is no longer necessary.”

Figure 4: Examples of virtual programming on the NOIRLab Events Webpage. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

Looking ahead, the Journey Through the Universe program in Hawai‘i is being adapted for virtual delivery in March 2021 and is expected to include elements similar to those used in the Viaje al Universo program.

As NOIRLab moves forward and adapts existing programs across sites in Chile, Tucson and Hawai‘i, lessons learned in adapting to social distancing have provided excellent opportunities for CEE staff to work together under difficult circumstances and find innovative solutions. In the process, the challenges of COVID-19 have helped CEE staff to bond, broken down barriers, and prepared us for a confident future of mutual, coordinated E&E programming.